

PREPARATION OF PROJECT DOCUMENTATION FOR THE INVENTION OF A UNIT OF THE DANUBE INSTITUTE ONMA FOR TREATMENT AND DISINFECTION OF BALLAST WATER OF SEA VESSELS

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Abstract

The article reveals the tasks in the programme of scientific grant Ukraine-Turkey, which is based on an invention of Danube Institute ONMA Ukraine on treatment and disinfection of ballast water of sea vessels according to the International requirements D-2.

In the article scientific selection of real type of vessels with possibility of typification and creation of working project with the purpose of its offer to International ship owners for installation on sea vessels is made.

The article shows the possibilities of the laboratory installation of the Danube Institute for disinfection and purification of ballast water of sea vessels of different sea areas.

Keywords. Ballast tanks, deadweight, azone, spatzia, invasives, grant, D-2 requirements.

Introduction. New requirements for the treatment and disinfection of ballast water of sea vessels in accordance with the requirements of D-2, required scientists and engineers of the Danube Institute of ONMA, to create a modern installation that would provide ships in accordance with the requirements of the new International Convention for the Protection of Bioresources of the World Ocean.

As a result of painstaking labour of the Institute's team a laboratory installation was created, which received a patent for invention and a patent for utility model. Continuation of scientific work allowed to win the Ukraine-Turkey Grant on ballast water treatment and disinfection. The work of two teams from the Danube Institute of ONMA Ukraine and the State Maritime University of Turkey, allowed the study of the waters of: the Black Sea, the Mediterranean Sea, the Sea of Marmara and the Igean Sea. The Ukrainian installation showed a high level of ballast water treatment in the above mentioned seas. At the request of the Turkish side, Ukraine donated documents for the establishment of its installation in the laboratory of the University of Turkey, which allowed analyses of treated water in the laboratory of Istanbul.

In accordance with the implementation plan of the Grant, the Danube Institute undertook to carry out a detailed design of its laboratory installation, which will be offered to International Ship Owners, thus ensuring its competitiveness to the World companies producing ballast water treatment and disinfection installations for ships.

The project will be executed for the DWT 7600 t vessel. It will be typified for different types of vessels of a certain tonnage. The customer of the detailed design is based on the quantitative indicator of similar displacement of the vessels.

Problem Statement. For a long time, the International Maritime Fleet has been discharging ballast water spontaneously, carrying invasive aliens, harmful viruses and bacteria from one navigation area to another.

These actions constantly, caused damage to fauna and flora, as well as led to global epidemics of coastal countries, ports of call of sea vessels.

Analysis of recent studies and publications. Recent studies conducted under the Scientific Project (grant): researchers Danilyan A.G., Tiron-Vorobyeva N.B., Zalozh V.I., found a number of harmful elements in the waters of the southern seas of Turkey and Ukraine, which were tested in the laboratory facility of the Institute with positive results. The laboratory certified by international certificates was confirmed to treat the water with positive results. Based on these studies, a number of scientific articles have been published in various publications. The publication of the book by our colleagues and partners: O.V. Gavrilov, O.I. O.V. Gavrilov, O.I. Sagaidak, O.M. Shumilo International regulation of pollution of the marine environment. Odessa vidvo "Transport" 2021 p. 389 c.

Highlighting previously unresolved details. common problem. It should be recognised that earlier requirements for ballasting and deballasting of ships were quite loyal to ship operators. There were no strict norms on ballast water treatment and disinfection.

Purpose of the article. (Purpose of your research). The purpose of the article is to reveal the issue of preparation of the D-2 Project from the laboratory installation to the creation of a ready working draft, which will be offered in wide access to shipowners of international companies.

Fig. 1. Laboratory installation of the Danube institute OMA for ballast water treatment and disinfection.

1-ballst water tank; 2-shut -of velva (DN-15); 3-coarse filter (50 microns); 4-pump (60 l/m); 5-ptessure gauge 0-6 bar; 6-air compressor; 7-ozone generator; 8- fine filter (1 micron), 9-ultraviolet radiation chamber; 10- tank purified disinfection water.

Outline of the main material. Scientists and engineers of the Danube Institute of the National University ONMA, created a laboratory installation for treatment and disinfection of ballast water of ships in accordance with the requirements of D-2, which received a patent for invention and a second patent for utility model. Later the scientific work of the Institute was highly appreciated by winning the Ukraine-Turkey Grant. Joint work of Ukrainian and Turkish scientists allowed to provide research of ballast water of southern seas: Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Aegean Sea and Marmara Sea. Analyses of treated ballast water at the Danube Institute's facility were carried out by certified laboratories of Turkey and Ukraine, and all treated water at the laboratory facility met all normative requirements

D-2. From 2024 all ships must have an approved Ballast Water Treatment System in accordance with the D-2 standard (see below). Existing ships are required to install the approved system, which can cost up to USD 5 million per ship. To facilitate implementation, IMO has published 14 guidance documents on the Convention, including Guideline G-2 on Balast Water Sampling, Guideline G-4 on Balast Water Management and Guideline G-6 on Balast Water Exchange. As of Veresen 2020, 79 countries participate in the BWM Convention.

All vessels built in 2017 must comply with the D-2 requirements, and the remaining vessels, as mentioned above, must undergo refit in 2024. This process

of ship re-equipment was delayed for a long time due to a number of objective and subjective reasons. On the one hand, not all shipowners managed to accumulate the necessary amount of funds for re-equipment and on the other hand, ship-repair plants are not able to ensure timely fulfilment of this work.

Practically all states in the coastal zones of the World Ocean suffer from the loss of aquatic diversity, fish catches have sharply decreased, and some species of valuable fish have disappeared altogether. Invasive aliens from other rivers, seas and oceans carried in ballast water have become a clear threat to the economies of a number of countries in this water are also carried pathogenic elements - bacteria and viruses, leading to global epidemics. That is why the world community has defined in the new D-2 rules the treatment and disinfection of ballast water. Alien organisms travelling across the oceans in the ballast water of ships pose significant problems for the marine environment, public property and human health. Unlike oil spills and other marine pollution caused by shipping, exotic organisms and marine species cannot be removed by cleanup or absorbed by the oceans. Once introduced, they are virtually impossible to eradicate, and in the meantime they can have devastating consequences. Specific examples include the introduction of the European zebra (*Dreissena polymorpha*) into the Great Lakes of North America, which has resulted in billions of dollars in pollution control costs and clean-up of overgrown underwater structures and waterways, and the introduction of the

American ctenophore (*Mnemiopsis leidyi*) into the Black Sea and the Sea of Azov, which has led to the near cessation of anchovy and sprat fisheries. The bacterium *Vibrio cholerae* (cholera vibrio) has been displaced from Asia to Latin American coastal waters, probably as a result of water ballast discharges, and Dinoflagellates of *Gymnodinium* and *Alexandrium* species originating from South-East Asia, which cause paralytic shellfish poisoning in humans, have been dumped in Australian waters, damaging local shellfish sanctuaries.

It should be noted that some countries (e.g. California) also consider silt, sand and other bottom soil adhering to anchor chains and anchors as sediment and require them to be washed as part of sediment control. Similarly, fouling of ship hulls is also a potential source of harmful aquatic organisms and should be removed as a matter of good management practice. Sediments are usually removed every three to five years when a vessel undergoes a special inspection and dry dock repair. Sludge is removed more frequently if the accumulated amount requires it. The amount of accumulated sludge depends on the ship's design and operating practices. Receiving equipment for sediments is usually only available in dry docks and ship repair facilities that traditionally deal with them. Employees who are in-

involved in the handling of sediments should be "International Marine Pollution Prevention Regulations" informed of the possible risks to human health associated with sediments from ship ballast tanks. They should also be appropriately trained and provided with appropriate protective clothing and equipment. Regulation B-5 of the ISM Convention requires all ships to remove precipitation from spaces intended for the carriage of ballast water in accordance with a Ballast Water Management Plan.

Purification and disinfection of ballast water sediments during ship operation is practically impossible, which gave the author of the article an opportunity to try to solve this problem together with the designer and project executor, scientists of the Danube Institute, when designing the working installation, and later to offer the installation to shipowners with the innovation of sediment treatment in ballast tanks.

A dry cargo vessel with a deadweight of 7,600 tonnes was selected for the standard detailed design. ...where a ballast water treatment and disinfection plant (according to the project) will be located in the engine room on two platforms. The hull configuration (outline) of the vessel does not allow to place all the equipment on the lower platform of the engine room, so part of the equipment will be placed on the upper platform, which is larger in area than the lower one.

Fig. 2. Shaft line and machine room plan for installation of ballast water treatment and disinfection system.

Conclusions. The rearmament of the World Marine Fleet according to the D-2 standard, is dictated by the Global danger of loss of fish species and contamination of waters of the coastal countries of the World Ocean by pathogenic bacteria and viruses. It can be assumed that the situation with ecological danger of contamination and resettlement of harmful invasive species

will increase in the future and will require new solutions for impact on the water areas of the planet.

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